

Career opportunities for Classical Dancers and Musicians

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Received: 15-06-2023 ; Accepted: 01-08-2023 ; Published: 09-05-2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11162817>

ABSTRACT:

This research paper explores different career opportunities for classical dancers and musicians available. It provides insights about advantages of studying performing arts specific to classical dance and music with respect to knowledge, artistic skills, management skills and communication skills. Research deals with in-depth analysis of benefits of choosing performing arts as career which in turn enhance skills. Knowledge - Analysing and understanding characters emotions and motive, understanding ideas with respect to historical background, profound knowledge on language, collate and contrast concepts, critical thinking, implementing techniques. Artistic Skills - creativity, ability to focus and practise vigorously for extended periods of time, create and emote. Management Skills - program planning, precise and detailed work, collaborating with other artists, time management, prudence, making best use of available resource. Communication Skills - briefing on concepts of the performance, oratory skill, communicating concepts creatively. The paper intends to unfold different possible career opportunities for classical dancers and musicians based on divergent streams such as Performance, Design and Production, Academic, Health and other fields which students can opt their career path in the journey as a performing artiste. Further it explores multiple possibilities under each steam. Performance - Performer, Choreography, Acting, Modelling, Anchoring, Creative Director, Instrumental musician, Vocal musician, Nattuvanār, Composer. Design and Production - Lighting Designer, Costume Designer, Makeup Artist, Property and Stage designer, Sound designer, Director. Academic - Teacher/Professor in schools/colleges, Dance historian or scholar, Lyricist. Health - Dance therapist, Music therapist, Yoga Instructor. Other - Dance

Photographer and Videographer, Performance critic, Art administrator, social media influencer. Research methodology followed is combination of descriptive design as existing career options are observed and Exploratory as exploring further options available. Possible limitations in this study, Limitation of access to data – access to multiple career options available. Limitation of Time – Time available to study topic in detail due to time constraints given to researcher. Limitation of research Design used – specific constraints might be on population of research based on selected design that might impact conclusion. Study provides gist of available types of academic courses for performing arts specific to classical dance and music, advantages, disadvantages of traditional learning against academic learning. This paper enables students to explore various career opportunities and accessibility of those options through different platforms. Information here can be used by academic organizations to improve their curriculum and aid students in the field of performing arts.

KEYWORDS:

Performing Arts, Career Opportunities, Classical Dancer

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Introduction

A profession in performing arts is best described as imaginative, skilful, creative, atypical. We have multiple fields in performing arts Dance, Drama, Music, Acting. These are generally thought of as hobbies and cannot be regarded as mainstream occupations for whatever reason. Over the period white collar jobs occupied the spotlight in the stage of career and cornered the performing arts. As social media's influence among students continues to expand, arts in India are becoming more and more well-liked. More young people and students are considering careers in the performing arts as time and thoughts evolved to show broader perspective in choosing their career paths.

This research paper is subjected to multiple opportunities that students can opt for as their career in the field of performing arts explicitly focusing on Indian Classical Dance and Music. It deals with

the advantages of studying performing arts in terms of knowledge, artistic skills, management skills and communication skills. The main objective of this paper is to explore numerous streams under Indian Classical Dance and Music a student and artiste can ponder their thought upon to take up as career such as Performance, Design and Production, Academic, Health and others. Paper also provides insights on advantages of pursuing performing arts with respect to Knowledge enhancement, Artistic skills, Management skills, Communication skills.

Literature Review:

The following elements were examined to compare alternative theories and to gain a wider perspective on the subject. Some of the articles and papers were referred for this research paper. Career Paths For Arts Students (ADITYA, 2021) , To Be or Not to Be (an Arts Major): Career Aspirations and Perceived Skills of Graduating Seniors Across Multiple Disciplines (Miller, 2016), Career in Performing Arts and Other Related Opportunities (Tandon, 2022). These articles have information on career paths and related opportunities. It deals with some of conventional roles that one can opt for as an artist. However, does not cover aspects of advantages and disadvantages of pursuing performing arts, dynamic roles an Indian classical artist can have while working in the field of performing arts. These articles also does not include merits and demerits of traditional learning of classical art form against academic learning.

Benefits of pursuing in Performing arts

Besides commonly known benefits like physical fitness, concentration, memory there is lot more undivulged benefits of pursuing performing arts.

1. Enhances the knowledge: When a dancer is playing a role of a character its utmost importance to have profound information on that character, one must analyse and understand characters emotions and motive so that same can be communicated to the audience in most creative manner. While performing a dance drama

especially on Indian Historical epics the background work done will augment knowledge on historical concepts. While working with different language compositions like Sanskrit, Tamil, Kanada and others, it increases the knowledge on those languages. One will be exposed to collate and contrast. Improves critical thinking and implementing the learnt techniques while choreographing.

2. **Artistic Skills:** It is utmost important how an artist can creatively express the intent and emotions underlying the story plot which builds creativity in artist. Indian classical dance requires ability to focus and practise vigorously for extended period. Dancer should have the capability to create and emote.
3. **Management Skills:** Event planning and organizing the performances develops management skills, artists must work with detailed and should be precise. To create opportunities to perform one must collaborate with other artists. It also builds time management, prudence, ability to make use of available resources.
4. **Communication Skills:** Briefing on the concepts of the performance improves oratory skills and communicating the concepts creatively. (ADITYA, 2021)

Career opportunities for Classical Dancers and Musicians:

Based on Performance:

Artiste exhibits their talent to the world. The concept here is to create and present the art form. The story/theme is told in most creative way that entertains and reaches the audience (Tandon, 2022). Skills required: Creativity and Originality, Knowledge and Practice, Stamina, Networking and Collaboration. Different roles an artist can opt under performance stream are as given below.

Dance Performer – Perform in different platforms, Choreographer – Choreograph the dance for different dance productions, Acting and Modelling – Acting and Modelling in art films and projects, Anchoring – Anchor the Dance or Music shows, Creative Director

– Creative Director for dance companies, Instrumental musician – Support the performance with instrumental music, Vocal musician – Vocal concerts and vocalist for dance performance, Nattuvanār – Much required rhythm for dance performance, Composer – Music composer for dance drama productions.

Based on Desing and Production:

Design is the artistic method using which a thought is manifested. It is moulded by the standards that determine its goal. Comparing and contrast of vision to provide unique value to the artwork. Skills required: Decisive, Detail oriented, Visualization, Techniques and Technology. Different roles an artist can opt under performance stream are as given below. Lighting Designer - Work with Directors to design the light pattern, colour, tone, placement, Costume Designer - Desing the costume based on character which may show-case historical theme or as per cast's requirement, Makeup Artist - They enhance the look and appearance of the performer, Property and Stage designer – Work on setting up stage sets for production or shows, Sound designer – Control the sound system for the live performances, Director - A production's visual vision needs to be supervised and unified, which is the responsibility of the art director.

Based on Academic:

Keeping the learning cycle alive, passing the acquired knowledge and skills to students through teaching in traditional classrooms and many other forums. Competitive exams like NET being conducted to be eligible for certified teaching profession in classical dance forms and one can serve in universities. Teacher must know the empirical and conceptual aspects of specific art form. Different roles an artist can opt under performance stream are as given below.

Teacher/Professor: Teach students both theoretical and practical aspects of Dance and Music, Dance historian or scholar: Contribute to the History and unexplored areas and concepts of the subject to bring it to the rest of the world with their research work, Lyricist: Articulate the concept and idea into production with profound

knowledge on language and pen down the idea into scripts.

Based on Health:

Combination of knowledge of Art and Human anatomy, physical, emotional and psychological aspects would lead one to become a therapist, Healing the ailments of human through Dance and Music has always been fruitful, dealing with ill people, elderly people, disabled people, veterans, and trauma survivors, as well as exploring mind-body techniques through study and practice. Dance therapist: Using Dance to treat both physical and psychological disorder, Music therapist: Using Music for curing ailments, Yoga Instructor: With the knowledge of yoga one can become yoga instructor and relate it to the requirements of the dancer's body as classical dance and yoga go hand in hand.

Other Categories:

Dance Photographer and Videographer: There is a different angle to the click when it is coming from an artist who practice the art form, Performance critic: With good hold on language and ability to observe and describe to give review of the performance, Art administrator: All the activities associated with artistic performances are planned, organized, promoted, and managed by an arts administrator (Team Leverage Edu, 2022), Social media influencer: With increase in indulgence of social media classical dancers turning into social media influencers.

Conclusion:

With growing technology and mindset even unconventional career in Performing arts can become exciting and satisfying if artists possess the passion and love towards the art form. With all possible academic courses and traditional learning methods that present modern world is offering, enables students to convert their passion into profession. Career opportunities for performing arts has become more accessible through social media, networking and even job portals. Information here can be used by academic organizations

to improve their curriculum and aid students in the field of performing arts.

Nothing comes without hard work, dedication, practice, and perseverance.

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Funding:

This study was not funded by any grant.

Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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